

Sales Prediction analysis using Machine learning Algorithm

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Abstract—Sales prediction analysis is one of the maximum crucial matters in an organization does. It fuels sales making plans and is used in the course of an organization for staffing and budgeting. Sales forecasting isn't always best approximately predicting your income numbers – it's approximately having the essential records that allows income leaders to make the right choices these days in order to help your enterprise be successful tomorrow. Despite its importance, many organizations use outdated practices that produce terrible forecasts. Here we are going to short analyse the concept of sales information and sales forecast. The sales prediction version become advanced using Random forest Classifier and Extra tree Classifier to predict business sales, and it became determined that the version turned into advanced to existing models. Using machine learning algorithms, a comprehensive examination of sales prediction is conducted.

Keywords—Accuracy, Machine Learning, Prediction model, Random forest classifier, Extra tree classifier

I. INTRODUCTION

The industry needs to do an assessment of customer behaviour with regard to the level of market acceptance for the product. This enables the sectors to introduce innovative products, which might be a major success and help the businesses avoid losing money on investments. The market's sales are typically predicted using a variety of techniques. Each of those approaches has a certain set of requirements that must be completed for the strategy to be successful. In general, forecasting is based on prior information that can be obtained from institutes relevant to their domains. Similar to this, when a new product is introduced to the market, there may not be any information available about it.

In our paper we have proposed the machine learning algorithms towards the data collected from the previous actual value of sales in a clothing store and forecast a predicted value using machine learning models. The algorithm used over right here are ML Classification algorithms is the best fit for this scenario.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

PAPER-1:

Purvika Bajaj et. al. [1] It is simple to predict sales for the upcoming years by taking into account past sales when

estimating future sales for Big Mart Companies. Models for machine learning are used to predict sales.

PAPER-2:

Rohit Sav et. al. [2] The resultant data may be used for predicting destiny income quantity with the assist of various system learning strategies for the stores like Big Mart. The use of XG improve Regressor method for predicting the income of an organisation like Big Mart and observed that the version produces higher result.

PAPER-3:

Sunitha Cheriyan et. al. [3] This study use understandable predictive algorithms to enhance future sales forecasts. The results are outlined in terms of the dependability and accuracy of effective prediction and forecasting techniques. Gradient Boost Algorithm, which exhibits the highest degree of predicting and futures sales prediction accuracy, has been shown to be the best fit model.

PAPER-4:

A. Gokilavani1 et. al. [4] Sales forecasting using prediction analytics algorithm is planned for providing a complete analysis of sales forecasting. The approach is performed on Departmental store. detect and correct the inaccurate dataset, fifth is data modelling, which is used to predict the data using machine learning the data from machine learning algorithm.

PAPER-5:

Naveen Kumar et. al. [5] Here we are going to briefly analyse the concept of sales data and sales forecast. In this research we have done a detailed study and analysis of models to improve the future sales.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

The proposed work provides an opportunity for accuracy of findings by implementing data exploration and analysis algorithms. The algorithms Random forest classifier and Extra tree classifier are chosen as it provide better results.

Random Forest Classifier

In order to increase the projected accuracy of the input dataset, the Random Forest classifier averages the results from multiple decision trees applied to various subsets of the input dataset.

Extra tree Classifier

A decision tree-based ensemble learning approach called ExtraTreesClassifier is used. Similar to RandomForest, ExtraTreesClassifier randomises some decisions and subsets of data to reduce over-learning from the data and overfitting.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The primary stage in predicting sales is model building. Algorithms are used by the user when developing the model.

1. Import the libraries required and then import and print the dataset.

```

In [1]: import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import os
import scipy as sp
import warnings
import datetime
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
%matplotlib inline

In [2]: data = pd.read_csv('myntra_products_catalog2.csv')
  
```

2. Training and Testing

```

In [37]: from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
x_train,x_test,y_train,y_test=train_test_split(x,y,random_state=0,test_size=0.2)

In [38]: print(len(x_train))
print(len(x_test))
print(len(y_train))
print(len(y_test))

1999
500
1999
500
  
```

3. Fit Random Forest Classifier to the dataset

```

In [43]: from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
rfc=RandomForestClassifier()
rfc.fit(x_train,y_train)

Out[43]: RandomForestClassifier()

In [53]: y_pred_rfc=rfc.predict(x_test)
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score,classification_report,confusion_matrix
from sklearn.metrics import r2_score
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error
print("Classification Report is:\n",classification_report(y_test,y_pred_rfc))
print("Confusion Matrix:\n",confusion_matrix(y_test,y_pred_rfc))
print("Training Score:\n",rfc.score(x_train,y_train)*100)
acc= accuracy_score(y_test,y_pred_rfc)
print("Accuracy:",(acc*100))
  
```

Classification Report is:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support	
0	1.00	0.75	0.86	8	
1	0.57	0.67	0.62	6	
2	0.92	0.92	0.92	225	
3	0.96	0.94	0.95	54	
4	0.00	0.00	0.00	3	
5	0.92	0.94	0.93	204	
accuracy				0.92	500
macro avg				0.73	500
weighted avg				0.91	500

Confusion Matrix:

```

[[ 6  0  2  0  0  0]
 [ 0  4  1  0  0  1]
 [ 0  2 207  1  0 15]
 [ 0  0  2 51  0  1]
 [ 0  1  2  0  0  0]
 [ 0  0 12  1  0 191]]
  
```

Training Score:
100.0
Accuracy: 91.8

4. Fit Extra Tree Classifier to the dataset

```

In [31]: from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier
etc = ExtraTreesClassifier(n_estimators=100, random_state=0)
etc.fit(x_train,y_train)

Out[31]: ExtraTreesClassifier(random_state=0)

In [42]: y_pred_etc=etc.predict(x_test)
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score,classification_report,confusion_matrix
from sklearn.metrics import r2_score
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error
print("Classification Report is:\n",classification_report(y_test,y_pred_etc))
print("Confusion Matrix:\n",confusion_matrix(y_test,y_pred_etc))
print("Training Score:\n",etc.score(x_train,y_train)*100)
acc= accuracy_score(y_test,y_pred_etc)
print("Accuracy:",(acc*100))
  
```

Classification Report is:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support	
0	1.00	0.62	0.77	8	
1	0.67	0.67	0.67	6	
2	0.92	0.89	0.91	225	
3	0.98	0.96	0.97	54	
4	1.00	0.33	0.50	3	
5	0.88	0.94	0.91	204	
accuracy				0.91	500
macro avg				0.91	500
weighted avg				0.91	500

Confusion Matrix:

```

[[ 5  1  2  0  0  0]
 [ 0  4  1  0  0  1]
 [ 0  0 201  1  0 23]
 [ 0  0  1 52  0  1]
 [ 0  1  1  0  1  0]
 [ 0  0 12  0  0 192]]
  
```

Training Score:
100.0
Accuracy: 91.0

5. Actual value and Predicted value

	Actual	Predicted
53	0	0
2391	5	5
2310	2	2
728	5	5
850	3	3
...	...	...
1810	2	2
2330	2	2
684	2	2
1674	2	2
2075	5	5

V. RESULTS

The performance of the machine learning algorithms are mainly focusing on accuracy. Companies are utilizing highly accurate machine learning models for proper business decisions.

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION FOR MACHINE LEARNING MODELS.

ALGORITHMS	ACCURACY
RANDOM FOREST CLASSIFIER	92 %
EXTRA TREE CLASSIFIER	91 %

In Classification models, accuracy can be calculated ,which indicates the good fit of a set of predictions to the actual or real values. Based on the results, we have determined that the Randomforest Classifier has an accuracy of 92% and the Extratree Classifier has an accuracy of 91%.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The overall performance is mainly focused on Accuracy. Machine learning techniques offers the effective mechanism in prediction. These ML techniques enhance the performance with better results and greatest predictability. In Future work, we will use other advanced ML algorithm to enhance the performance and we will use other feature selection techniques.

VIII. REFERENCES

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